

JOINT STRENGTH OF CO-CURED COMPOSITE STRUCTURES USING Z-PINNING PATCH

I. Choi^{1*}, J. Jeong², S. Cheong²

¹ Structures and Materials Dept., Korea Aerospace Research Institute, Daejeon, South Korea
(ihchoi@kari.re.kr),

² Dept. of Mech. & Automotive Eng., Seoul National University of Science & Technology, Seoul, South Korea

Keywords: *composite, co-cure, z-pin, z-pinning patch, single-lap, joint, strength*

1 General Introduction

Z-pinning technique is one of the methods to enhance the inter-laminar strength of laminated composites or to enhance the joint strength of co-cured composite jointed structures [1-3]. In this paper, the new ‘z-pinning patch’ concept for easy application in manufacturing factory, which was recently invented by authors, will be introduced. Single-lap joint specimens were successfully manufactured using the ‘z-pinning patch’ and those were tested to check the enhancement of joint strengths. Furthermore various z-pins with specially machined shape and/or chemically corroded surface were individually extracted to measure the effect of each condition of z-pin in joint strength.

2 Concept of Z-pinning Patch and Manufacturing

Figure 1 shows schematic concept of the z-pinning patch and Fig. 2 shows curing concept using it. In order to keep normal directional insertion of the patch sometimes a guide set like part number 41 and 42 in Fig. 2 may be needed. Figure 3 shows the apparatus to manufacture the z-pinning patch. Figure 4 shows a manufactured z-pinning patch and jagged shape of z-pin which is made of stainless steel.

Fig. 1 Concept of the z-pinning patch.

Fig. 2 Concept of z-pinning using the patch.

Fig. 3 Apparatus to manufacture the z-pinning patch.

Fig. 4 Z-pinning patch and jagged shape of z-pin.

3 Single-Lap Joint Test

Some single-lap joint test specimens were successfully manufactured using z-pinning patch. Two kinds of specimens with 6mm and 8mm thickness of jointed part were manufactured. Diameter of z-pin is 0.5mm. Two kinds of interval of z-pin are applied, which are 3mm and 2mm. The volume density of z-pin is 2.2% and 4.9%, respectively.

Figure 5 shows single-lap joint strength according to various specimen types. Although the specimens of 3mm interval does not show obvious enhancement of joint strength, but those of 2mm interval shows clear enhancement of joint strength, 54% for 6mm thickness of joint part and 68% for 8mm.

Fig. 5 Single-lap joint strength of various specimens.

Fig. 6 Failure shape of single-lap joints. (From top, no z-pinning, 3mm interval and 2mm interval)

Figure 6 shows failure shape of single-lap joint specimens with 8mm thickness of joint part. From top, failure shapes of no z-pinning and 3mm interval and 2mm interval of z-pins are shown. In case of 3mm interval, z-pins were extracted at middle surface of z-pinned joint structure. In case of 2mm interval, z-pins were partially extracted at lower part of z-pinned joint structure and remained part of it was not extracted at all until final failure happened, which failure mode was tensile breakage of composite structure, not separation of jointed parts.

4 Extraction Test of Individual Pin

Figure 7 shows two shapes of z-pin of 0.5mm diameter: one is the original shape without any machining or treating; the other is specially machined into jagged shapes and is chemically corroded. Fig. 8 shows a typical specimen manufactured in this study for the extraction test of individual z-pins.

Fig. 7 The original pin (up) and specially machined pin as jagged shape (down).

Fig. 8 The manufactured specimen for extraction test of individual pin

Figure 9 shows extraction force of various individual z-pins. Jagged shape of pin increases extraction force to about 10 times. Corrosion of pin increases it about 20% in case of 0.5mm diameter pin. Fig. 10 shows the typical extraction force histories of various z-pins. Six curves are arranged in sequence of magnitude of the average of the maximum peak value in the extraction force histories. The first uppermost curve is measured from the test of the jagged shaped and chemically corroded z-pin of 0.5mm diameter. The second uppermost curve is measured from the test of the jagged shaped z-pin of 0.5mm diameter. The two curves show a large magnitude of extraction force history and gradual

decrease of that magnitude through the full extraction procedure. Also, the two curves show corrugated shapes; the wavelength values of the curves corresponded well to the interval of the grooves of the jagged shape of the z-pins, as can be seen in Fig. 7.

- the Korean Society for Aeronautical and Space Sciences*, Vol. 37, No. 7, pp. 1-8, 2009.
- [3] Y. Park, B. Lee, J. Kweon, J. Choi and I. Choi, “The strength of composite bonded T-joints transversely reinforced by carbon pins”, *Composite Structures*, Vol. 94, pp. 625-634, 2012.

Fig. 9 Extraction force of various individual z-pins.

Fig. 10 Individual extraction force histories of various z-pins.

5 Conclusion

In this research, the concept of ‘z-pinning patch’ was proposed and it was applied to single-lap joint structure. The z-pins were specially machined to take jagged shape and chemically corroded for rough surface, consequently for tighter joint.

References

- [1] A. Mouritz, “Review of z-pinned composite laminates”, *Composite: Part A*, Vol. 38, No. 12, pp. 2383-2397, 2007.
- [2] I. Choi, S. Ahn, C. Yeom, I. Hwang and D. Lee, “Impact Resistance of Composite Laminates Manufactured by New z-Pinning Technique”, *J. of*